

Polymer Molecular Weight Prediction with No Dependence on Solvent Viscosity. A Quantitative Pulse Field Gradient Diffusion NMR Approach.

Francisco M. Arrabal-Campos[†], Pascual Oña-Burgos[†] and Ignacio Fernández^{*†‡}

[†] Department of Chemistry and Physics, ceiA3, Universidad de Almería, Ctra. Sacramento, s/n, Almería, E-04120 (Spain).

[‡] BITAL, Research Centre for Agricultural and Food Biotechnology, Ctra. Sacramento, s/n, Almería (Spain).

Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: To progress on the practical issues of molecular weight prediction via diffusion NMR, the first $\log(D\eta)$ vs $\log(Mw)$ Universal Calibration Curve (UCC) is provided, allowing with the only need of quantitative D-values and solvent viscosity, the easy and fast determination of molecular weight with no matter of the solvent used.

Diffusion NMR spectroscopy was developed by Stejskal and Tanner in the mid-1960s with the aim of measuring diffusion coefficients and estimate hydrodynamic radii of molecules in isotropic media.¹ C. S. Johnson, decades later, introduced the first two-dimensional output of this principle and initiated an outstanding number of publications where this methodology has been applied.² Currently, it is used to study mostly organometallic complexes, as well as supramolecular systems such as host-guest systems, helicates, grids, supramolecular polymers and more.³ Diffusion NMR has also found applications in studies of biosystems,⁴ pharmaceuticals⁵ and the structure of nanoparticles.⁶

The physical observable usually derived from the diffusion NMR experiment is the diffusion coefficient D.⁷ In extreme circumstances such as temperatures close to the freezing point of the solvent, the estimation of the solution viscosity has been also assessed.⁸ A number of empirical methods for relating diffusion coefficients to the molecular weight (Mw) have been proposed.⁹ The Williard group have applied this technique to correlate relative diffusion coefficients with Mw of reactive organolithium species.¹⁰ In the same line, the groups of Maddaluno and Oulyadi,¹¹ Mulvey,¹² among others¹³ have predicted reliable formula weights by using calibration curves built from adequate standards dissolved in the solvent where the analyte is

then measured. All the aforementioned literature, allude the estimation of molecular weights of small molecules compared to polymers. To address the practical issues of polymer molecular weight determination, the groups of Johnson first^{2b} and Grubbs and coworkers,¹⁴ among others¹⁵ years later, have developed accurate Mw determination methods via DOSY. In these, linear correlation between $\log D$ and $\log Mw$, is the basis for the prediction. The same methodology has been, later on, applied on amphiphilic block copolymers¹⁶ and L-Lactide polymers.¹⁷ In all of them, specific calibration curves were built for each solvent where the Mw was estimated, or the polymerization process occurred.

In general, the Stokes-Einstein equation¹⁸ and its modifications¹⁹ are useful and enable size estimations. However, Morris and coworkers have recently showed that it fails for small molecule diffusion and have proposed a simple method that rationalize the D values and their Mw.^{19a} In parallel with polymer Mw predictions,²⁰ the polydispersity index (PDI) has been also estimated employing the differential diffusion profile observed for main polymer chain signals versus the extremity signals,²¹ or with the application of gamma or log-normal distribution models.²²

In polymer science, the single frequency ITAMeD algorithm has been identified as the method of choice for monodispersed samples.²³ For nonsymmetrically distributed diffusion NMR

data, Xu and Zhang has recently presented an iterative regularization method based on Trust-Region Algorithm for the Inversion (TRAIIn).²⁴

We report herein the application of both ITAMeD and least-squares methods for the quantitative determination of the diffusion coefficients as it is discussed further below.

Diffusion NMR experiments in their most common form follow signal attenuation according to the Stejskal-Tanner (ST) equation.^{1a} With no temperature and concentration gradients, molecular displacements are achieved by approximating the experimental dependence of the spin echo signal on the PFG amplitude by a known analytical function.²⁵ The most common form is a Gaussian decay function in which D is the translational diffusion coefficient of the molecule to which the signal belongs, γ_{eff} is a linear combination of the gyromagnetic ratios of the nuclei studied depending on the coherence transfer pathway of the experiment, δ is the PFG duration and σ is the gradient shape factor (equation 1).

$$E_{diff} = e^{-D\gamma_{\text{eff}}^2\delta^2\sigma^2g^2\Delta'}$$

The diffusion delay Δ' is corrected by an amount that depends on the specific pulse sequence and gradient shape used as described by Sinnaeve *et al.*²⁵ As mentioned before, the size of a molecule, as represented by its equivalent hydrodynamic radius r_H , is related to D by the Stokes-Einstein equation.¹⁸ For a molecule with non-ideal shape and size, the equation can be modified as described by Kharlamov and Latypov (equation 2),²⁶ where $c(r_s, R_h)$ is the coefficient which includes the relative size of the molecule and the solvent; and $f(a,b)$ is the factor related with the non sphericity of the molecule.

$$D = \frac{kT}{c(r_s, R_h)f_s(a, b)\eta R_h}$$

In polymer science however, is mass rather than geometrical features what is often important, and especially the empirically derived Flory scaling relationship (equation 3)²⁷ is probably the most straightforward relation between Mw and diffusion coefficient.²⁸

$$D = AM_w^{-\alpha}$$

Delsuc and coworkers have checked the validity of this power law equation for a large set of molecular types and molecular weights, introducing α as a measure of the fractal dimension d_F ($= 1/\alpha$).²⁹ This new exponent has proven to be dependent on the molecular structure under study, where the dimensionality reflects the geometry of the interactions between solute and solvent. In other words, fully isotropic interaction between solvent and object should give a d_F of 3. These authors established d_F to be in the range of 1.41 to 2.56 for polymers and globular proteins,^{29a} but 2.96 for hollow clusters ranging from 0.2 to 30 kDa.^{29b}

Further, Grubbs and coworkers,¹⁴ have employed equation 4, derived for the first time by Williard *et al.*,^{10c} to linearly relate

D and Mw, which incorporates the density of the molecule (ρ) and the Avogadro constant (N_A).

$$\log(D) = -\frac{1}{3}\log(M_w) + \frac{1}{3}\log\rho - \frac{1}{3}\log\eta - \frac{1}{3}\log\left(\frac{162\pi^2}{k^3T^3N_A}\right)$$

If equation 4 would be correct, the 1/3 term would always be a constant between $\log D$ and $\log M_w$, which it is not the case. For this reason, the work reported by Pollack³⁰ is key in order to understand what we will discuss further below, and it opens up a more complex situation than the one described by equation 3. He stated that the dependence of D with viscosity is a power law what significantly departs from the Stokes-Einstein equation, and eventually assigns the interaction with the viscous media and not the shape of the object as the critical factor.

Over Pollack's work we have reconsidered equation 2, and obtained equation 5 as a linearized relation which is independent on viscosity, and therefore allowed us to estimate polymer molecular weights with the use of just one external calibration curve (see supporting information).

$$\log(\eta D) = -\frac{1}{3\beta}\log(M_w) - \frac{1}{\beta}\log\left(\frac{c f_s K^{1-\beta}\eta^{\beta(\beta-1)}\left(\frac{3}{4\rho N_A\pi}\right)^{1/3}}{kT}\right)$$

The term η^β , and thus β , describes the aeolotropic interaction between solvent and object. When a solute molecule is in a solvent environment, its functional groups interact with the inherent structural requirements of the solvent, and its presence can impose an alternate structuring pattern on the adjacent solvent molecules. Such solvent structuring is often invoked to explain the properties of certain solutions.³¹ Liquid structuring and its associated entropy are generally responsible for much of the behavior of polymer systems, such as the folding of globular proteins and the formation of lipid bilayers and micelles.³² The organization of solvent molecules around a particular solute will in general involve both positional and orientational correlations with the specific chemical architecture of the solute, and thus will vary in its details from one class of solute to another. In this context, the β coefficient introduced in this communication, is equal to Delsuc's fractal dimension over three, or three times the inverse of the α coefficient (equation 3). Importantly, to the best of our knowledge, the different authors have always been in the need of creating external calibration curves, for each solvent in which the analyte wanted to be studied. We report herein the way of predicting these Mw's with only one calibration curve measured at one specific solvent.

From our equation 5, one can built a $\log(D\eta)$ vs $\log(M_w)$ plot where the β value could be obtained from the slope of the linear fit (Figure 1). This new approach represents the first universal calibration curve (UCC) for Mw prediction of polymers with no dependence on the solvent used.

For its construction we employed monodisperse polystyrene polymers between 0.5 and 1000 kDa of molecular weight (P1 to P7 in Figure 1, Tables S4 and S5). Benzene was the solvent of choice due to its high viscosity (η 0.646 cP at 21 °C) and its extensive use in polymer science thanks to its solvation abilities.³³ It is worth mentioning that all PFG-STE measurements

were performed at 0.9 mg/mL, in the validity range of Flory's law (i.e. absence of obstruction or concentration effects on diffusion measurements).²⁷ For each of the polymers P1 to P7, the processed spectra from the 24 gradient values were stored and analyzed through the DiffAtOnce package (LMS, Figure 1)³⁴ or the corresponding Matlab® script provided recently by Urbanczyk *et al* (ITAMeD, Figure 1).²³

Figure 1. Universal Calibration Curves (UCC) for Mw prediction.

The combination of the slope of this curves with equation 5, yields as mentioned above, a power law behavior with a β -value of 0.587, that corresponded to a fractal dimension d_F of 1.70 ($1/\alpha$) in Delsuc nomenclature.^{29a} Our values are very close to the α values reported in the literature for polyethylene oxide ($\alpha = 0.62^{2b}$, 0.589^{15b}), polystyrene ($\alpha = 0.537^{14}$, $0.47-0.61^{29a}$, 0.554^{15b}), and poly(L-lactide) ($\alpha = 0.598$),¹⁷ what confirm our set of measurements. In fact, α values are predicted to be between 0.6 and 0.5 for a fully solvated polymer chain and 0.33 for collapsed polymer chains.³⁵

In order to prove our new UCC curve and demonstrates its applicability to any solvent, we proposed as a proof of concept the determination of the Mw of polystyrene samples dissolved in benzene, chloroform, THF and toluene. The standard Bruker pulse sequence, incorporating one short spoil gradient pulse (step1s1d), was used for all the experiments assayed. Figure 2 shows a rendering of the raw PFG-STE data for polymer P2 in benzene- d_6 .

Figure 2. Raw PFG-STE data showing the aromatic region of sample P2 in benzene- d_6 , showing with an asterisk the five monitored signals and with # the one overlapped with the benzene satellite.

The advantage of ITAMeD over the traditional least-squares method is provided by the following example. Fitting of the signal at δ 7.00 ppm (denoted with # in Figure 2), that is sum of polystyrene and benzene satellite signals, produces an erroneous averaged D-value when using least-squares ($4.55810^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and a perfect separation of both components when ITAMeD is applied ($4.208 \cdot 10^{-10}$ for P2 and $22.215 \cdot 10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ for benzene (see Figure S3-S4 in the supporting information).

Table 1 shows the results afforded from the PFG-STE measurements of polystyrene P2 and P6 in four different solvents, i.e. benzene- d_6 , tetrahydrofuran- d_8 , chloroform- d_1 and toluene- d_8 . The corresponding ($D\eta$) values of the eight samples were fitted to the UCC to calculate their corresponding Mw. As a matter of fact, the eight values were 1396, 1218, 1343 and 1418 Da for P2, and 437.746, 421.308, 400536, 395009 for P6, with differences in mass below 6.7 and 9.8 %, for P2 and P6, respectively (Table 1). According to published data, an error in the determination of Mw by PFG-NMR is accepted to be not higher than 10%.^{15b} Thus, the use of our UCC does not decrease the accuracy of the state of the art quantitative estimation of polymeric Mw.

Table 1. Diffusion values ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and UCC-predicted Mw for P2 and P6 in four different solvents.

Solvent	Polymer	$D\eta$ (10^{-3})	Mw (Da) ^b	diff (%) ^c
Benzene- d_6	P2	2.7407	1396	5.8
THF- d_8	P2	2.9056	1218	4.5
CDCl_3	P2	2.7523	1343	5.0
Toluene- d_8	P2	2.7270	1418	6.7
Benzene- d_6	P6	0.1046	437746	4.8
THF- d_8	P6	0.1068	422510	8.1
CDCl_3	P6	0.1067	422712	8.1
Toluene- d_8	P6	0.1091	414482	9.8

^a ^1H PFG-STE measurements were performed at room temperature. We calculated the middle diffusion coefficient of those aromatic signals that provide fittings with R2 higher than 0.9999. See Supporting information ^b Estimated via the ITAMeD universal calibration curve $y = -0.5682x - 1.775$ ($R^2 = 0.9993$). ^c Taking the commercial values of 1320 Da for P2 and 460000 Da for P6 as a reference. See supporting information.

In addition, the extrapolation of the calibration curve to a lower molecular range, allowed the prediction of the residual non-deuterated benzene, tetrahydrofuran, chloroform and toluene, with variations in mass (ΔMw) of 5.6, 8.1, 34.9 and 2.5 % (Table 2).

Table 2. Diffusion values ($\text{m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and UCC-predicted Mw for the residual non-deuterated solvent of samples of P2.

Solvent	D (10^{-10}) ^a	$D\eta$ (10^{-3})	Mw (Da) ^b	diff (%)
Benzene- d_6	21.19	1.3687	82.5	5.6
THF- d_8	28.14	1.3609	82.5	8.1
CDCl_3	25.20	1.4140	77.7	34.9

^a ¹H PFG-STE measurements were performed at room temperature. ^b Estimated via the ITAMeD universal calibration curve $y = -0.5682x - 1.775$ ($R^2 = 0.9993$).

In the case of chloroform (entry 3, Table 2), which has the larger error in the prediction (34.9 %), one has to consider that the volume of chlorine is not proportional to its atom weight and therefore its Mw is underestimated due to this reason. The same applies for potassium and iodine cations, which have similar radii (1.38 and 1.33 Å, respectively) but significantly different weight (39 Da and 127 Da, respectively). This problematic has been previously reported.¹³

To prove further our UCC, we used the D-values described by Delsuc and coworkers for several polymers in different solvents with a wide range of molecular weights.^{29a} Tables S21-S26 show the results of predicting the Mw via their corresponding $D\eta$ values with equation 5, and their comparison with their known weights. Numerical optimization gave a relative error between real and predicted Mw below 5%, illustrating the strength of our UCC.

Along the same line of thought, one can assume that this UCC will serve for those non-polymeric systems which solute-solvent structuring could be ascribed to the same β -value of 0.587. In fact, when considering the D-values of the more than 40 analytes discussed by Morris and coworkers in toluene- d_8 and chloroform- d_1 ,^{19a} and again, representing their Mw with those predicted through our UCC, even though obtained at a temperature four degrees below (294 vs 298 K), more than 40% of those molecules fit extraordinarily well (errors in Mw estimation below 10%), due to the fact of having similar positional and orientational correlations with the specific chemical architecture of the solvent (see Tables S27 and S28).

In conclusion, we have introduced a universal calibration curve (UCC) for the successful prediction of molecular weights of linear and narrowly dispersed polystyrene-based polymers with the only need of the quantitative D-value and the viscosity of the solvent. Plots of $\log(D\eta)$ versus $\log M_w$ showed excellent linearity, and the agreement between PFG-STE calculated and actual weight appeared excellent, even in small molecules. The model is presented in a desktop application available at <http://www2.ual.es/NMRMBC/downloads/UCCPolymerPrediction.rar>. Continuing studies are in progress in order to apply β -values in polydisperse polymers, and molecular density estimations.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Complete NMR diffusion data (10 figures and 28 tables). This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

AUTHOR INFORMATION

Corresponding Author

* E-mail: ifernan@ual.es

Notes

The authors declare no competing financial interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was supported by the Junta de Andalucía (Spain) under the project number P12-FQM-2668 and by Bruker Española SA. Special thanks are due to AIMPLAS (Plastics Technology Center) for the supply of polystyrene samples.

REFERENCES

- 1 a) Stejskal, E. D.; Tanner, J. E. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1965**, *42*, 288-292.
b) First use of a pulsed gradient stimulated echo: Tanner, J. E. *J. Chem. Phys.* **1970**, *52*, 2523-2526.
- 2 a) Johnson, C. S. *Progress Nucl. Magn. Reson. Spect.* **1999**, *34*, 203-256; b) Chen, A.; Wu, D.; Johnson, C. S. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1995**, *117*, 7965-7970.
- 3 Avram, L.; Cohen, Y. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2015**, *44*, 586-602, and references cited therein.
- 4 a) Anslund, I.; Topgaard, D. *J. Magn. Reson.* **2009**, *200*, 250-254; b) Rodrigues, E. D.; Silva, D. B.; Oliveira, D. C. R.; Silva, G. V. J. *Magn. Reson. Chem.* **2009**, *47*, 1095-1100.
- 5 a) Occhipinti, P.; Griffiths, P. C. *Adv. Drug Deliv. Rev.* **2008**, *60*, 1570; b) Trefi, S.; Gilard, V.; Balaýssac, S.; Malet-Martino, M.; Martino, R. *Magn. Reson. Chem.* **2009**, *47*, S163-S173.
- 6 a) Marega, R.; Aroulmoji, V.; Dinon, F.; Vaccari, L.; Giordani, S.; Bianco, A.; Murano, E.; Prato M. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 9086; b) Canzi, G.; Mrse, A. A.; Kubiak, C. P. *J. Phys. Chem. C* **2011**, *115*, 7972-7978.
- 7 Pregosin, P. S.; Kumar, P. G. A.; Fernández, I. *Chem. Rev.* **2005**, *105*, 2977-2998.
- 8 Fernández, I.; Martínez-Viviente, E.; Pregosin, P. S. *Inorg. Chem.* **2004**, *43*, 4555-4557.
- 9 a) H. C. Chen and S. H. Chen, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1984, *88*, 5118-5121. b) A. Polson, *J. Phys. Colloid Chem.*, 1950, *54*, 649-652.
- 10 a) Li, D.; Hopson, R.; Li, W.; Liu, J.; Williard, P. G. *Org. Lett.* **2008**, *10*, 909-911; b) Liu, J.; Li, D.; Sun, C.; Williard, P. G. *J. Org. Chem.* **2008**, *73*, 4045-4052; c) Li, D.; Keresztes, I.; Hopson, R.; Williard, P. G. *Acc. Chem. Res.* **2009**, *42*, 270-280; d) Li, D.; Kagan, G.; Hopson, R.; Williard, P. G. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 5627-5634; e) Kagan, G.; Li, W.; Hopson, R.; Williard, P. G. *Org. Lett.* **2009**, *11*, 4818-4821; f) Kagan, G.; Li, W.; Hopson, R.; Williard, P. G. *Org. Lett.* **2010**, *12*, 520-523; g) Li, W.; Kagan, G.; Yang, H.; Cai, C.; Hopson, R.; Dai, W.; Sweigart, D. A.; Williard, P. G. *Organometallics* **2010**, *29*, 1309-1311; h) Li, W.; Kagan, G.; Yang, H.; Cai, C.; Hopson, R.; Sweigart, D. A.; Williard, P. G. *Org. Lett.* **2010**, *12*, 2698-2701; i) Guang, J.; Hopson, R.; Williard, P. G. *J. Org. Chem.* **2015**, *80*, 9102-9107.
- 11 a) Lecachey, B.; Duguet, N.; Oulyadi, H.; Fressigne, C.; Harrison-Marchand, A.; Yamamoto, Y.; Tomioka, K.; Maddaluno, J. *Org. Lett.* **2009**, *11*, 1907-1910; b) Hamdoun, G.; Sebban, M.; Cossoul, E.; Harrison-Marchand, A.; Maddaluno, J.; Oulyadi, H. *Chem. Commun.* **2014**, *50*, 4073-4075; Consiglio, G. B.; Queval, P.; Harrison-Marchand, A.; Mordini, A.; Lohier, J.-F.; Delacroix, O.; Gaumont, A.-C.; Gerard, H.; Maddaluno, J.; Oulyadi, H. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2011**, *133*, 6472-6480.
- 12 a) Mulvey, R. E.; Armstrong, D. R.; Conway, B.; Crosbie, E.; Kennedy, A. R.; Robertson, S. D. *Inorg. Chem.* **2011**, *50*, 12241-

-
- 12251; b) Armstrong, D. R.; Garcia-Alvarez, P.; Kennedy, A. R.; Mulvey, R. E.; Robertson, S. D. *Chem. - Eur. J.* **2011**, *17*, 6725-6730; c) Armstrong, D. R.; Kennedy, A. R.; Mulvey, R. E.; Parkinson, J. A.; Robertson, S. D. *Chem. Sci.* **2012**, *3*, 2700-2707; d) Hevia, E.; Kennedy, A. R.; Mulvey, R. E.; Ramsay, D. L.; Robertson, S. D. *Chem. Eur. J.* **2013**, *19*, 14069-14075.
- 13 Neufeld, R.; Stalke, D. *Chem. Sci.* **2015**, *6*, 3354-3364.
- 14 Li, W.; Chung, H.; Daeffler, C.; Johnson, J. A. Grubbs, R. H. *Macromolecules* **2012**, *45*, 9595-9603.
- 15 a) Viel, S.; Capitani, D.; Mannina, L.; Segre, A. *Biomacromolecules* **2003**, *4*, 1843-1847; b) Barrere, C.; Mazarin, M.; Giordanengo, R.; Phan, T.; Thvand, A.; Viel, S.; Charles, L. *Anal. Chem.* **2009**, *81*, 8054-8060; c) Kuzmina, N. E.; Moiseev, S. V.; Krylov, V. I.; Yashkir, V. A.; Merkulov, V. A. *J. Anal. Chem.* **2014**, *69*, 953-959.
- 16 Bakkour, Y.; Darcos, V.; Li, S.; Coudane, J. *Pol. Chem.* **2012**, *3*, 2006.
- 17 Lewinski, P.; Sosnek, S. *Pol. Chem.* **2015**, *6*, 4353-4357.
- 18 $D = kT/(6\pi\eta r_H)$, where r_H is the hydrodynamic radius, D the diffusion coefficient, k the Boltzmann constant, T the absolute temperature and η the solvent viscosity.
- 19 (a) Evans, R.; Deng, Z.; Rogerson, A. K.; McLachlan, A. S.; Richards, J. J.; Nilsson, M.; Morris, G. A. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* **2013**, *52*, 3199-3202; (b) Macchioni, A.; Ciancaleoni, G.; Zuccaccia, C.; Zuccaccia, D. *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2008**, *37*, 479-489.
- 20 a) Mark, J.; Ngai, K.; Graessley, W.; Mandelkern, L.; Samulski, E.; Koenig, J.; Wignall, G. *Physical Properties of Polymers*, 3rd ed.; Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 2004. b) Flory, P. J. *Principles of Polymer Chemistry*; Cornell University Press: Ithaca, NY, 1953.
- 21 Vieville, J.; Tanty, M.; Delsuc, M-A. *J. Magn. Reson.* **2011**, *212*, 169-173.
- 22 Roding, M.; Bernin, D.; Jonasson, J.; Sarkka, A.; Topgaard, D.; Rudemo, M.; Nyden, M. *J. Magn. Reson.* **2012**, *222*, 105-111.
- 23 Urbanczyk, M.; Bernin, D.; Kozminski, W.; Kazimierczuk, K. *Anal. Chem.* **2013**, *85*, 1828-1833.
- 24 Xu, K.; Zhang, S. *Anal. Chem.* **2014**, *86*, 592-599.
- 25 Sinnaeve, D. *Concepts Magn. Reson.* **2012**, *40A*, 39-65.
- 26 Kharlamov, S. V.; Latypov, S. K. *Russ. Chem. Rev.* **2010**, *79*, 635-653.
- 27 a) Flory, P. *Principles of Polymer Chemistry*, New York: Cornell University, 1953; b) Edwards, S. F.; Doi, M. *The Theory of Polymer Dynamics*; Oxford University Press: New York, 1986.
- 28 Where A is a molecule dependent constant and α is a coefficient that depends highly on the shape of the particle.
- 29 a) Auge, S.; Schmit, P.-O. Crutchfield, C. A.; Islam, M. T.; Harris, D. J.; Durand, E.; Clemancey, M.; Quoineaud, A.-A.; Lancelin, J. M. Prigent, Y.; Taulelle, F.; Delsuc, A. *J. Phys. Chem. B* **2009**, *113*, 1914-1918; b) Floquet, S., Brun, S., Lemonnier, J. F., Henry, M., Delsuc, M. A., Prigent, Y.; Cadot, E.; Taulelle, F. *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2009**, *131*, 17254-17259.
- 30 Pollack, G. L. *Phys. Rev. A.* **1981**, *23*, 2660-2663.
- 31 a) Stillinger, F. H. *Science* **1980**, *209*, 451-457; b) Israelachvili, J.; Wennerstrom, H. *Nature* **1996**, *379*, 219-225.
- 32 Cesaro, A. In *Thermodynamic Data for Biochemistry and Biotechnology*; Hinz, H. J., Ed.; Springer-Verlag: Berlin, 1986; pp 177-207.
- 33 Viscosity was taken from www.knovel.com.
- 34 DiffAtOnce® is a registered program developed by I. Fernández and F. M. Arrabal-Campos in the University of Almería. **2013**.
- 35 A fully solvated chain occurs in a solvent when the polymer-solvent interactions predominate over polymer-polymer interactions, whereas a collapsed chain occurs in a poor solvent where polymer-polymer interactions dominate. See for instance: a) Wilkins, D. K.; Grimshaw, S. B.; Receveur, V.; Dobson, C. M.; Jones, J. A.; Smith, L. J. *Biochemistry* **1999**, *38*, 16424-16431; b) Zhao, T.; Beckham, H. W. *Macromolecules* **2003**, *36*, 9859-9865.